

D8.3

Atmospheric subdomain implementation plan

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Deliverable abstract

The RIs of the ENVRI atmospheric subdomain have conducted a comprehensive analysis of the FAIRness of their data management. The identified gaps considered most important from a user perspective concern the following FAIRness functions:

- Findable: globally unique identifier; indexed in searchable resource.
- Accessible: (meta)data retrievable by standardised protocol
- Interoperable: common vocabulary
- Re-usable: established license, documented provenance, (meta)data meets community standards.

The tasks for implementing these functions were grouped by the following criteria:

1. Importance of the function for the user
2. Maturity of the function in the RI
3. Accordingly, the tasks were grouped into 3 categories:
4. Immediate implementation: the function implemented is highly important for the user, the implementation plan is consolidated.
5. Immediate implementation planning: the function implemented is highly important for the user, the implementation plan needs to be refined, know-how at the RIs needs to be established.

Task for second half of project: the function implemented is considered important, but implementation can be postponed to allow focussed work on the highly important FAIRness functions.

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3465753>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services

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1. Introduction & Procedure

The ENVRI-FAIR project's objective is to implement "FAIRness" for data produced in the European Research Infrastructures (RIs) organized in the Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) community, in order to make them ready for connecting to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In this context, "FAIR" is an acronym comprising the aspects of "Findable", "Accessible", "Interoperable", and "Reusable" as specified by the FORCE11 community.

ENVRI-FAIR WP8 organises and conducts this implementation work for the community of ENVRI RIs in the atmospheric subdomain, comprised of the RIs ACTRIS, EISCAT, IAGOS, ICOS, and SIOS. This deliverable constitutes a plan for implementing data FAIRness functionality in the data production of the atmospheric ENVRI RIs. It is based on assessments of the current data handling functionality in relation to the requirements defined by the FAIRness principles by each of these five RIs.

These assessments were conducted on several occasions:

- By means of a questionnaire during the writing process of the ENVRI-FAIR project proposal □
During a workshop under the ENVRI-FAIR kick-off meeting in January 2019.
- During a workshop of ENVRI-FAIR WP8 11-12 June 2019 in Amsterdam
- During a virtual WS 11-12 December 2020
- in ENVRI-FAIR Deliverable D5.1 (Requirement analysis, technology review and gap analysis of environmental research infrastructures).

This deliverable condenses the identified FAIRness issues common to all or most atmospheric ENVRI RIs into WP8 implementation tasks for the first part of the project.

The timing of the internal milestones and deadlines in this deliverable do not take into account possible changes and delays forced by the world-wide corona virus situation. As the situation is 20 March 2020, we do think this work can proceed as planned in this deliverable.

2. Task List

The implementation plan consists of tasks organised into three groups:

1. Essential tasks where the specification is mature and which are considered very important as to begin implementation immediately.
2. Essential tasks which are considered very important, but where the specification is in need of clarifications before implementation can begin. Further clarification of specification, i.e. implementation planning, should start immediately.
3. Tasks which are considered relevant for implementing data FAIRness, but are considered less important than the tasks in the first 2 groups. These tasks are scheduled for the second half of the project.

2.1. Tasks for immediate implementation

The implementation progress of the tasks in this group is monitored by WP8 Task 8.4 (Implementation of FAIR roadmap in the Atmospheric subdomain RI) under the responsibility of project partner NILU. Each RI in the atmospheric ENVRI RI is individually responsible for working on these tasks.

RI implementation responsible persons: Damien Boulanger (IAGOS), Markus Fiebig (ACTRIS), Ingemar Häggström (EISCAT), Alex Vermeulen (ICOS), Lara Ferrighi (SIOS)

2.1.1. Consolidation of consistent use of PIDs throughout data production workflow

The work on this task is based on ENVRIplus deliverable D6.1 on data identification and citation, which provided the initial analysis, specification, and implementation plan for this task. In this first implementation plan, Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) were to be used for final data products, whereas Persistent Identifiers for eResearch (ePIC) or equivalent handle PIDs were to be used for most of the other identifiable items in the data production workflow (software, data pre-products, instruments, ...).

Since ENVRIplus deliverable D6.1, a number of PID types dedicated to various identified entities have been introduced, and have received wider acceptance. Since PID identification of entities involved in data production is a prerequisite for documenting data provenance and its numerous use cases, the ENVRI atmospheric sub-domain decides to take these additional PID types into use, and proceeds with their implementation. The PIDs recommended by ENVRI-FAIR WP8 are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Identified items in data production workflow, including PID and metadata schema used.

Identified entity	PID type	metadata schema
humans	ORCID	ORCID record schema
organisations	Research Organisation Registry (ROR)	
instruments	Persistent Identifiers for eResearch (ePIC)	Persistent Identification of Instruments (PIDINST)
data products	Persistent Identifiers for eResearch (ePIC)	RI schema, complete metadata
	Digital Object Identifier (DOI) (mandatory)	DataCite
data pre-products	Persistent Identifiers for eResearch (ePIC)	RI schema
physical samples	Persistent Identifiers for eResearch (ePIC)	RI schema
	International Geo Sample Number (IGSN)	IGSN schema
software	Persistent Identifiers for eResearch (ePIC)	RI schema, complete metadata
	Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	DataCite

Identification of data products by DOIs shall extend to products delivered on a real-real-time (RRT, within 3h of measurement) or near-real-time (NRT, within 3 days of measurement). Recommended implementation strategies include:

- Annual DOIs per station per instrument providing RRT or NRT data, where the DOI is coined at the start of a year and filled with data during the year. Referencing the DOI needs to include date and time of access. This implementation strategy needs more maintenance, but allows to budget data use by station, instrument, instrument PI, funding organisation, etc.
- One DOI for the whole RRT / NRT data product of an RI, which is filled with data over time. Referencing the DOI needs to include at least date and time, preferably also the part of the product accessed by specifying a fragment. This strategy is easier to implement, but has few options for assessing data use.

Expert contact point for further details on the implementation is Maggie Hellström in ENVRI-FAIR WP5.

2.1.1.1. ACTRIS Implementation Plan - PID

The ACTRIS data centre (DC) PID system will be homogeneous over DC units, in order to identify all entities involved in data production across all its thematic units. The PIDs used in ACTRIS correspond to those listed in the table above for the entities included there. In addition, ACTRIS uses ePIC PIDs, for identification of QA / QC documents.

Since the DC units serve as primary data repository for ACTRIS data products in their thematic area, the DOIs for these products will be issued at the DC unit level. To facilitate homogeneous accounting of data provision and use, all ACTRIS DC units will offer at least one common granularity of data product DOIs, one DOI per annual dataset for each individually identified instrument.

For identification of RRT / NRT data, ACTRIS will use constant DOIs with continuously updated content, quoted by including an access date. Options for the granularity of RRT/NRT data DOIs include one DOI for the whole NRT product per variable provided by the DC unit, and one DOI for each RRT/NRT data stream coming from an individually identified instrument.

Milestones in implementing PIDs in ACTRIS DC:

- July 2020: determine solution for handle PIDs. Done: conclusion to use ePIC PIDs.
- March 2022: implement primary DOIs for all final data products in primary repositories with homogeneous granularity per repository, resolving contributions of individual principal investigators (PIs) and research performing organisations (RPOs), thus facilitating accounting of data use by means of DOIs.
- December 2022: implement PIDs for data pre-products.
- December 2022: implement ORCIDs for humans and RORs for organisations.

2.1.1.2. *EISCAT_3D Implementation Plan - PID*

EISCAT is implementing the metadata specification, using the exposed DataCite metadata fields. This includes assigning a DOI for each Data Collection and PIDs for the Data Sets therein. At least for higher level data sets, the B2Handle system seems most suited.

To secure provenance documentation, the data sets will be referenced by unique IDs of the underlying data (allowing database queries) and PIDs of the processes operating on it, including both software PIDs and hardware PIDs. This is planned for all levels of data, from the lowest voltages samples to the final data products.

Milestones in implementing PIDs in EISCAT:

- November 2021: Determine granularity levels Data Collections for DOIs.
- January 2022: Implement DOIs for all data products based on Data Collections in primary repositories..
- June 2022: Implement machinery to publish PIDs for data used in publications.

2.1.1.3. *IAGOS Implementation Plan - PID*

IAGOS final data products (from data processing level 2 to level 4) have DOIs minted by the IAGOS Data Centre (provided by AERIS). Only one DOI is minted by data product (e.g. Observational Times series L2). DOI fragments will be soon proposed for citation of a subset of the product (e.g. query of the user). Some public documents are also assigned with DOIs (e.g. QA/QA documents).

Using the service provided by AERIS, IAGOS will mint ePIC PIDs for all entities managed by the Data Centre, including data sets under level 2, instruments, software, documents, etc. So far, those entities have home-made identifiers. The data production workflow will be updated to integrate the minting of PIDs for each entity, involving:

- Assigning PIDs to all existing entities: fine data sets (i.e. time series for a flight) including version control, sensors, QAQC documents, software, etc.
- Updating the workflow to automatically assign PIDs to new entities
- Having all members of the IAGOS team with an ORCID and integrating the information into the data production workflow

This task is mandatory to be able to implement the provenance in the IAGOS workflow. Thus this work will be jointly done with to the task “Consistent documentation of provenance throughout data production workflow”.

Milestones:

- September 2020: definition of the new data production workflow with PID management (done)
- May 2021: ePIC registration using AERIS solution (done)
- October 2021: Implement ORCID for humans and ROR for organisations
- December 2021: management of DOI fragments and implementation of a querystore
- December 2021: consistent use of PIDs and new data production workflow implemented

2.1.1.4. *ICOS Implementation Plan - PID*

ICOS has already implemented from its onset minting of Handle PIDs (through ePIC) in the repository for all data objects, including raw data. PIDs are assigned during the machine-to-machine ingestion of the data objects or the creation of a collection. Next to this ICOS also mints DataCite DOIs for either the individual data objects of higher level data products and/or collections of data objects. A DOI minted by ICOS always refers to the PID on the data object or collection and shares the same landing page. All data is available through HTTP GET under the ICOS CC4BY licence.

All landing pages are human and machine readable and provide metadata in a number of standard metadata exchange formats that are selected through content negotiation for machine-to-machine communication or by selecting the respective link on the landing page by the human user. Provenance and other metadata of the landing pages is generated dynamically from the ICOS RDF triple store.

2.1.1.5. *SIOS Implementation Plan - PID*

SIOS does not assign or manage PIDs for the contributing centres, which have full ownership of the datasets provided via the SIOS data portal. On the other hand, SIOS recommends having DOIs in place, and the different data centres are aligning to this recommendation. In this context, SIOS is also working

on identifying core data, i.e. with particular relevance for the key questions within Arctic research, which shall require a DOI.

2.1.2. Common standard interfaces for metadata and data access

Efficient machine-to-machine (M2M) interfaces to both metadata and data are a prerequisite for virtually any services processing RI produced data further, e.g. indexing portals, visualisation services, or virtual research environments (VRE) offering data analysis tools. Depending on the nature of the service, two types of interfaces are in use:

- Interfaces based on existing standards, offering a high degree of generic reusability, but limited functionality.
- Interfaces based on Representational State Transfer (REST), which offer more functionality, but currently are not standardised, albeit being readily documented, and thus offer little reusability.

WP8 partners agree that atmospheric ENVRI RIs need to offer both types of interfaces to cater to different types of users and use cases. Depending on the use case, both types of interfaces are recommended.

Concerning standardised metadata M2M interfaces, WP8 considered the following:

- **Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) interface serving metadata in ISO19115 format with WMO Information System (WIS) profile.**
- Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) interface serving metadata in ISO19115 format with Infrastructure for spatial information in Europe (INSPIRE) atmosphere profile.
- **Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW)**
- OGC Sensor Observation Service (SOS)

The two options marked in bold font are the ones agreed within WP8 (in contact with WP7 and WP5) for recommended implementation due to their widespread use and associated advantages of re-using implementations. Users of these protocols include, among others, WMO Global Atmosphere Watch World Data Centres and GEOSS.

Concerning standardised data M2M interfaces, the workshop considered the following:

- Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol (OPeNDAP), a protocol for accessing structured data through the web. Allows for sub-setting and streaming of data, thus well suited for web applications.
- OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS), for accessing structured data, allows sub-setting, transfers of files for client-side processing.
- OGC Web Mapping Service (WMS), for accessing structured data, provides rendered map products of gridded data.

Each of these interfaces is targeted to different types of data. Thus, depending on the nature of the data produced by the RI, any of the interfaces mentioned above may be used.

This task will also comprise the interoperability for metadata and data exchange within the ENVRI atmospheric subdomain.

2.1.2.1. ACTRIS Implementation Plan - machine-to-machine interface

The ACTRIS data centre (DC) consists of 5 distributed topic DC units: for data from surface in situ stations; surface-based aerosol remote sensing data; surface-based cloud remote sensing data; surface-based trace gas remote sensing; atmospheric simulation chambers. While the topic DC units serve as primary data repositories, discovery and access to ACTRIS data is provided by a common portal, in an integrating DC unit. This DC unit also hosts a common, continuously updated ACTRIS DC metadata repository for discovery of data through the portal. The internal metadata profile of this repository will cover items contained in common standardised, domain-specific profiles, but will go beyond these to cover topic specific use metadata.

ACTRIS metadata will be served by the ACTRIS DC metadata repository connected with the ACTRIS data portal. This will include M2M interfaces, both classic standardised and REST ones, e.g. an OAI-PMH interface serving ISO19115 metadata with WMO profile. The served metadata records will include a direct link to the data, where the access protocol will depend on the data type (OPeNDAP, OGC-WCS).

Milestones:

- First version of ACTRIS DC metadata repository available (December 2021).
- OAI-PMH interface serving ISO19115 metadata with WMO profile for ACTRIS data available, will include links for data access. (September 2022).

2.1.2.2. *EISCAT_3D Implementation Plan - machine-to-machine interface*

EISCAT metadata access

EISCAT plans to make metadata harvestable in formats including DataCite and possibly other standards. The existing EISCAT archive of analysed data (<https://madrigal.eiscat.se/madrigal>) has been migrated to a new version, Madrigal 3, with HDF5-based archival. An OAI-PMH server for harvesting metadata is planned to be added to Madrigal 3 and B2FIND will harvest its metadata. The Madrigal database has API script examples available for several high-level languages (python, Matlab and IDL). Similar routines will then be added to the DIRAC portal for EISCAT 3D data and the DIRAC file catalogue will be extended accordingly.

EISCAT data are the property of EISCAT Scientific Association and low-level data should not be copied outside the EISCAT e-infrastructures without consent. Future EISCAT 3D users will use DIRAC to search and stage data, submit analysis jobs and retrieve the results. All metadata and approved data products are generally open for any non-military and non-commercially use. We also consider using notebooks for users to upload their own analysis software. At present, the protocol for these interactions needs to be decided.

Milestones:

- June 2020: DataCite metadata attributes defined for level 3 data (done)
- November 2021: DataCite metadata attributes defined for level 1/2 data
- January 2022: Metadata ingestion into B2FIND
- January 2022 : Interface OAI-PMH to the DIRAC file catalogue

2.1.2.3. *IAGOS Implementation Plan -- machine-to-machine interface*

Metadata Access

IAGOS metadata are available and harvestable through a Geonetwork server that serves metadata, in ISO19115 format with INSPIRE profile. Two endpoints are available: CSW and OAI-PMH. IAGOS is also developing a web REST API in order to serve metadata in JSON format.

Data Access

IAGOS will implement a THREDDS server that will allow to serve IAGOS data through standardized protocols:

- OPeNDAP service for all data sets (time series and gridded data)
- WCS and WMS services for gridded data sets

IAGOS is also implementing a web REST API in order to serve data sets to users who need machine-to-machine access. Data will be delivered in the same formats as on the IAGOS Data Portal (NetCDF and Nasa Ames) and in JSON.

Milestones:

- November 2021 : REST API for metadata access
- December 2021 : REST API for data access
- March 2022 : THREDDS server implemented with access to all IAGOS products

2.1.2.4. *ICOS Implementation Plan -- machine-to-machine interface*

The gaps identified for improvement of the fairness of the ICOS repository concern mainly small details and refinements that nevertheless are important for implementing future machine to machine interoperability. Until now the main emphasis in the development has been on pure functionality through a robust, flexible and modern core (back-end), and achieving a high scalability and performance of the system. Next steps are on core functionalities for the users, for access, preview and attribution of the data providers.

Planned improvements and time schedule:

1. Metadata provision:

- Metadata tags on landing pages following schema.org to enable for Google data search harvesting (9-2020) (done)
- Implement OAI-PMH export of metadata to feed higher level data collection metadata into GEOSS (12-2020)
- Publish the ICOS ontology as controlled vocabulary (12-2020)

- Implement a ISO19135 XML format landing page (12-2020) (implementing WIS at the same time as WIS is a weak subset of ISO19135) (superseded by DCAT-AP profile, done)
 - Extend the metadata with related documents, datasets, images, software, and other resources (6-2021) (done)
 - Add license information as resolvable URL on the landing pages (4-2021) (underway)
 - Extend the provenance metadata to the full ICOS processing chain (7-2021) (partially done)
2. **Data access**
- Implement a ENVRI standard RESTful API for data subsetting (12-2021)
 - Implement the export of ICOS timeseries as NetCDF-CF files (12-2020) (ATC)
 - Updating the current THREDDS (possibly ERDDAP for compatibility with the marine subdomain) service to the latest version and connecting this to the ICOS metadata and data objects (6-2021) (underway)
3. **User interface**
- Increased search capabilities for spatial extent, conditions and free text keywords (9-2020) (done)

2.1.2.5. *SIOS Implementation Plan -machine-to-machine interface*

Metadata access: SIOS is planning to expose all metadata provided by the data portal through a common CSW catalogue. Steps for doing this:

- deployment of pycsw software (summer 2020)
- indexing of METNO data in pycsw using ISO 19115-2 (end of 2020)
- implementation of OAI-PMH at NILU and CNR (end of 2020 and summer 2022)
- integration of partner data in central pycsw (end of 2021)
- translation to INSPIRE (March 2022)
- translation to WMO Core profile (summer 2022)

Data access: OPeNDAP is already available for some contributing centres, some have already started implementing the protocol which should be finalized during 2020. Specifically:

- NILU OPeNDAP implementation (December 2020)
- CNR OPeNDAP implementation (Summer 2022)

In order to expose additional relevant information in the (meta)data catalogue additional tasks will be required:

- update of internal metadata profile to support link to WIGOS and URL for licences (June 2020)
- reconfigure indexing engine to support new data model (end of 2021)

2.1.3. Indexing of data resources in WIS, GEOSS

For meeting the FAIR requirement of “Findable”, data needs to be discoverable in relevant data search portals.

The following data discovery portals were considered:

- **Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS).**
- **WMO Information System (WIS)**
- Google Dataset Search: considered not specifically relevant to atmospheric community, but relevant to other users, can be considered at a later stage.
- European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): currently no mature data search interface available □
WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WIGOS): still under development.

The WP8 workshops decided to focus on connecting to the portals displayed above in bold font due to the combination of relevance to the atmospheric community and maturity.

This task is connected to ENVRI-FAIR WP3, which in Task 3.3 works on the liaison with international stakeholders.

2.1.3.1. *ACTRIS Implementation Plan -link to WIS, GEOSS*

ACTRIS will serve metadata by standardised interface, OAI-PMH, and in ISO19115 format with WMO profile. These are exactly the metadata exchange specifications for the WMO Information System (WIS). ACTRIS will therefore connect to WIS by setting up a link to its closest Global Information System Centre (GISC) in WIS.

WIS is continuously harvested by the GEOSS. Thus, by linking to WIS, ACTRIS data will be discoverable in GEOSS as well.

Milestones:

- Metadata link between ACTRIS metadata repository and closest GISC in WIS established (November 2022).

2.1.3.2. *EISCAT_3D Implementation Plan -link to WIS, GEOSS*

Work at EISCAT has been directed towards the ESPAS ontology, <http://ontology.espas-fp7.eu/vocabs>, as the GEOSS fields have not been sufficient. The plan is to revisit the proposed ones. It has to be taken into account that use of Google Search is impossible for the EISCAT Associates in China.

Milestones:

- October 2021: ESPAS ontology entered into datasets.
- October 2021: Define an atmospheric parameter set for EISCAT_3D suitable for WIS and GEOSS
- December 2021: links with WIS established for the existing atmospheric data sets

2.1.3.3. *IAGOS Implementation Plan -link to WIS, GEOSS*

IAGOS serves metadata through standard interface such as CSW and OAI-PMH and will also implement the WIGOS metadata profile in the framework of its link with GAW. These are the metadata exchange specifications for the WMO Information System (WIS).

As WIS is continuously harvested by GEOSS, by linking IAGOS to WIS, IAGOS data will be discoverable in GEOSS as well.

Milestones:

- December 2021 : implementation of WIGOS metadata profile
- December 2022: link with WIS established

2.1.3.4. *ICOS Implementation Plan -link to WIS, GEOSS*

The ICOS repository is fully searchable through an open SPARQL endpoint that also allows to access the complete ontology in OWL. Furthermore, there are several graphical web interfaces for human search and access to the data. Currently there is no connection to WIS for greenhouse gas observations. WMO collects greenhouse gas observations through the World Data Centre for Greenhouse Gases (WDCGG) and maintains station metadata through the OSCAR database. The WDCGG does not have a machine-to-machine interface for metadata and data exchange. It requires at the moment that individual PIs enter manually the metadata and data into their portal and then the data is processed in several manual steps for publication. The WDCGG is still far from being a FAIR repository and therefore publication on WDCGG has little added value. A request to allow ICOS in the role of recognized WMO GAW contributing network to submit station metadata to WMO OSCAR on behalf of the station PIs is pending. June 2021 WDCGG provided the necessary json metadata templates that will be used for metadata exchange of the ICOS Level 2 releases. WDCGG will make use of the ICOS minted DOIs and will work on automatic data usage updates at ICOS CP from the downloads from their platform. The GEOSS portal allows upload of metadata in CKAN standard, which will be implemented by ICOS at the end of 2021.

2.1.3.5. *SIOS Implementation Plan -link to WIS, GEOSS*

This task is related to the finalization of pyCSW. Once this is done, we will connect through WIS primarily, and directly to GEOSS for some datasets. We need however to create guidelines on this to avoid multiple paths for the data in question.

Milestones:

- WIS link: December 2022

2.1.4. Common use of authentication schemes

The authentication scheme is a subject that clearly goes beyond the sub-domains as it is very technical and not specific for the services. It also is a common requirement for all RIs. As it is deeply connected to the architecture of the systems it has a strong influence on workflows and security of the systems. As many RIs already have systems that are (partly) operational, changes in this basic functionality are not

easy, risky and can easily turn out to be expensive. However, from the perspective of user experience a single sign on for all services of ENVRI will be very valuable.

The authentication, authorisation and identification system will be studied in ENVRI-FAIR in a separate task force that will report at the end of 2020 with recommendations for the whole domain. Although waiting for this report carries the risk that for some RIs stages are passing where decisions are made that are difficult to revert, we consider that it is nevertheless essential to agree on a common approach for the domain, also connecting to the developments in the framework of EOSC and making use of the efforts and experiences in the framework of the AARC and AARC2 projects.

Meanwhile, the RIs in the atmospheric subdomain will follow a strategy of non-regret where operational choices are made to support the current workflows and daily work in the RIs. Adding or further building on support for Oauth2 in the AAI systems will then allow for a transition to more harmonized approaches in the second half of the project that is transparent to the users. Implementing Oauth2 and linking to login through ORCID will allow to make use of the ORCID institutional login through SAML and at the same time will promote the use of ORCID for identification of persons. The tiered approach follows two consecutive steps where step 1 is implemented in 2020 and step 2 follows in the course of 2021 if this step is approved by the ENVRI community.

1. User authentication via [Open Researcher and Contributor ID \(ORCID\)](#)
2. [The Blueprint Architecture](#) developed by the H2020-funded initiative [Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration \(AARC\)](#), which connects to ORCID

This task is to link to the respective efforts in ENVRI-FAIR WP5, which defines interoperability requirements for the whole of ENVRI-FAIR.

2.1.4.1. ACTRIS Implementation Plan -authentication schemes

In the ACTRIS Data Centre (DC) as distributed data centre, the authentication schemes need to be aligned with national policies and infrastructures of the contributing partners.

In this setting, ACTRIS will focus on ORCID as common an authentication solution across the RI. Authorisation handled decentrally. TF2 recommended authentication solution will be implemented once determined. If the TF2 recommendation won't be provided in time, ACTRIS will consider Google authentication as additional alternative.

Milestones:

- ORCID implemented for authentication across ACTRIS DC (December 2021, postponed to December 2022)

2.1.4.2. EISCAT_3D Implementation Plan -authentication schemes

EISCAT is working on EGIcheckin for authentication. EGIcheckin brokers a selection of Idps, like EDUgain, B2access, ORCID, and other social identities such as QQ and WeChat. In addition, there will be a local login for users outside of the general Idp services, and for a second level authentication for wizard/expert users.

For authorisation, it is planned to setup a local ldap server, using as much as possible automatic selection procedures from the Idp provisions. For some users it is needed to add EISCAT specific rules,

Milestones:

- EGI Checkin implemented for authentication on EISCAT portal for operations (June 2021, OK)
- EGI Checkin implemented for authentication on EISCAT portal for data (October 2021)
- EGI Checkin implemented for authentication on EISCAT portal for processing (October 2021)

2.1.4.3. IAGOS Implementation Plan -authentication schemes

Currently IAGOS has a homemade authentication system. Users have a IAGOS account and use a simple login/password connection. A new version of the IAGOS data portal is currently under development. In this frame a new authentication / authorization system will be implemented.

A solution developed by the French Atmospheric Data and Services cluster AERIS and based on the tool Keycloak will be used. It will allow to provide Single Sign On system through ORCID, eduGAIN or a local AERIS users database. It will be easy to connect to other similar system if needed.

Milestones:

- March 2022: AERIS authentication implemented in new IAGOS Data Portal and then ORCID and eduGAIN authentication operational

2.1.4.4. *ICOS Implementation Plan -authentication schemes*

ICOS already supports SAML and OAuth2 for login, next to a local login on the basis of the user email address that can be mixed and matched. When the choice for a common AAI scheme is made, it will be integrated in the current system in 2021.

2.1.4.5. *SIOS Implementation Plan -authentication schemes*

The SIOS data portal gives free and open access to data without any authentication needed, if not for further processing of data using local infrastructures. Authentication in this case is done within the content management system (Drupal) in use. SIOS is currently not prioritizing this task, although the implementation of EduGain as SSO is looked at with interest. SIOS will participate into the dedicated task force (AAAI) to closely follow the discussion on the topic.

2.1.5. Endpoint for providing service metadata to ENVRI-hub

The ENVRI-hub will build onto the ENVRI Catalogue of Services, which is specified and implemented by Task Force 1 (TF1) of WP5. TF1 has decided that metadata on services are to be provided by the ENVRI RIs using the [Data Catalogue Vocabulary \(DCAT\)](#) applying the [DCAT Application Profile for data portals in Europe \(DCAT-AP\)](#). Further details are in the process of specification in TF1. In the final implementation, the ENVRI-hub will harvest the ENVRI Catalogue of Services.

The ENVRI-hub pilot intends to set up a demonstrator for the ENVRI-hub in parallel with the ongoing specification work in TF1. In order to make most efficient use of project resources, the ENVRI-hub pilot will re-use the metadata and data APIs developed by WP8 RIs in the context of WP8 task 8.5. WP8 RIs are to interact actively with ENVRI-hub pilot developers to establish this connection.

This implementation task works together with and is dependent on further guidance by:

- WP5 TF1 concerning details of the DCAT-AP profile.
- WP5 TF6 concerning the details of transferring metadata to the ENVRI-hub pilot.
- WP7 concerning choices of technologies for implementing 1) generating DCAT-AP data and service metadata; 2) serving the metadata in the endpoint, which includes the dependence of technologies and the services possible to offer.

2.1.5.1. *ACTRIS Implementation Plan - endpoint towards ENVRI-hub*

ACTRIS participates in WP5 TF1, and has been using the tools provided there to register ACTRIS services with the ENVRI-hub pilot.

In the context of WP8 Task 8.5, ACTRIS will implement a Python API to its metadata and data sources to connect to the WP8 demonstrators. This interface will be re-used by the ENVRI-hub to facilitate uptake of ACTRIS resources into the ENVRI-hub.

Milestones:

- Setting up PythonAPI endpoint serving metadata and linking to data, serving both WP8 demonstrators and ENVRI-hub. (July 2022)
- Create record describing ACTRIS data provision services in ENVRI catalogue of services. (done)

2.1.5.2. *EISCAT_3D Implementation Plan - endpoint towards ENVRI-hub*

EISCAT is working in TF1/6 and will utilise the Madrigal pythonAPIs to in the ENVRI-hub services (task 8.5).. EISCAT is reformatting the internal databases and adding metadata sets to harmonise with ENVRIhub.

Milestones:

- Upgrade to madrigal 3.0 with python3 APIs (done)
- Harmonise Madrigal APIs with ENVRI services (June 2022)
- Implement APIs for all levels of data (December 2022)

2.1.5.3. *IAGOS Implementation Plan - endpoint towards ENVRI-hub*

IAGOS is part of TF1 and will use the proposed tools to enter the metadata of the services in the ENVRI catalogue of services.

IAGOS is leader of the task 8.5 and will develop a Python API that can be called within the task 8.5 demonstrator ([envri-wp8-demonstrator](#)) providing a list of platforms, variables mapped to ECVs and data

access. IAGOS is also part of TF6 and will contribute to the integration of the WP8 demonstrator in the ENVRI-Hub.

Milestones:

- October 2021: Setting up the PythonAPI endpoint serving metadata and linking to data, serving both WP8 demonstrator and ENVRI-hub
- December 2021: Create the records describing IAGOS data provision services in ENVRI catalogue of services

2.1.5.4. ICOS Implementation Plan - endpoint towards ENVRI-hub

As a demonstration ICOS already implemented a mapping of the ICOS metadata on the Level 2 datasets towards DCAT(-AP) and serving this through [the ICOS sparql endpoint](#). The sparql endpoint was queried by the CKAN software demonstrator of TF4 and the retrieved metadata exposed through CKAN's search interface, together with similar metadata from Euroargo.

ICOS will participate in the TF1 workshops and use the tools provided by EPOS to enter the metadata of the services in the ENVRI Hub catalogue. ICOS will also be active in TF6 and contribute to the development of the demonstrators, most notably the atmospheric footprint service

Milestones:

- April 2021: Setting up the mapping of ICOS metadata to DCAT-AP and exposing this through the ICOS sparql endpoint serving metadata and linking to data, serving both WP8 demonstrator and ENVRI-hub
- December 2021: Create the records describing relevant ICOS services in the ENVRI catalogue of services

2.1.5.5. SIOS Implementation Plan - endpoint towards ENVRI-hub

SIOS is part of the task 8.5 and will develop Python APIs that can be called within the task 8.5 demonstrator ([envri-wp8-demonstrator](#)) providing, for fixed land stations indexed in the SIOS catalogue, a list of platforms, variables mapped to ECVs and data access. The Python APIs are based on the pyCSW catalogue as implemented in Section 2.1.2.5 and data access is provided through OPeNDAP protocol.

Milestones:

- provide a list of python functions to retrieve information about selected datasets provided within the SIOS catalogue as designed within task 8.5 (end of September 2021)

2.1.6. Recommendations on RIs graphical user interfaces (GUI)

Graphical user interface (GUI) is one of the essential components of each WP8 data portal. GUI is a tool for users to easily access different services provided by an RI, such as digital objects, data visualizations and other relevant content. Many of the core FAIR requirements, such as PIDs, provenance and authentication, are natural components of a graphical user interface as well. Thus, GUIs supplement machine-to-machine interfaces that are also important but typically better serve operational data usage and more experienced users.

In order to satisfy FAIR requirements, WP8 GUIs should implement the following components:

- Search interface
 - Structured search with time, variable and location
 - Free text search if applicable
 - Semantic search (optional)
- Landing pages
 - PID resolvable landing page for each DO.
 - Tailored, additional landing pages for custom data sets and collections (optional)
 - Links to related data sets (optional)
- Visualizations
 - Static images
 - Dynamic images (optional)
- Provenance
 - Contact information, citing information and software version(s)
 - Full traceability of each DO (optional)
 - Free and open access to software (optional)
- Downloading
 - Free access to data and downloading of a single file

- Optional: Open access to data, downloading of multiple files, OPeNDAP / REST or similar end point, OGC Web services for data access, data display and data processing

2.1.6.1. *ACTRIS Implementation Plan - GUI recommendations*

ACTRIS is a large, distributed RI with 5 different thematic data units (In-Situ, ARES, GRES, ASC and CLU). DVAS is the 6th ACTRIS unit, hosting the ACTRIS data portal (<https://actris.nilu.no>) and linking to the data archived in the topical data centre units. The ACTRIS data portal contains all the metadata from the individual units, and provides a single-entry point for users searching and accessing various ACTRIS data. The ACTRIS data portal will be compliant with the recommendations stated in this task.

Because the whole ACTRIS RI and its separate data units are currently developing at rapid phase, the existing ACTRIS portal will undergo complete revision in the forthcoming years to better a) meet the FAIR requirements and b) support the common metadata schema and various new services provided by the units. In early 2021, a pilot project was conducted to experiment with the new metadata schema, and to practice modernizing the technology stack and outlook of the portal. The actual development of the new ACTRIS data portal GUI has started with the goal of releasing a beta version for testing in 2022.

Milestones:

- End of year 2021 - Kick Off development of the new ACTRIS data portal. Done.
- 2022 - Release of revised ACTRIS data portal GUI beta version for test users.
- 2023 - Release for public.

2.1.6.2. *EISCAT_3D Implementation Plan - GUI recommendations*

EISCAT is running portals for operation, low-level data and high-level data. They are developments of a structure suitable for the current systems. With the construction of EISCAT_3D, the increased complexity of operations and substantially larger data volumes, structurally new portals are developed. To approach the FAIR requirements, some additions to the current portals will be implemented, mainly to enable an easier transition to the newer systems,

Milestones:

- Spring 2021 - Upgrade to the Madrigal vs 3 database for the high-level data (done)
- Mid 2021 -New data format for basic high-level data (done)
 - HDF5 format
 - Increased metadata with proper descriptions of parameters
 - Added provenance metadata
 - DataCite metadata
- End of 2021 -Proper AAI for embargoed data with EGI-Checkin and group management
 - Jupyter notebooks for user access to data
- 2022 - EISCAT_3D operations portal
 - Dirac data management system

2.1.6.3. *IAGOS Implementation Plan - GUI recommendations*

The IAGOS Data Portal is the central and unique access point of all IAGOS data products and services. A new version of the portal is under development and is planned to be delivered by early 2022. This new version is based on the CMS Wordpress in which are integrated web components developed in VueJS. All dynamic features are developed in VueJS in order to be independent from the CMS and then easily integrable in any new system used in the future.

Some features are already developed:

- REST API for data and metadata access developed in Java
- Authentication system allowing access through ORCID or EduGAIN federation, with token generation for access through the REST API (authentication is required for download)
- Dynamic visualisation of each IAGOS flights time series and vertical profiles: inter-comparison of all the parameters for a flight, visualisation of the data on a map, inter-comparison between several flights, etc.
- Rich metadata representation

Most of the features of the new portal are under development or planned :

- Faceted search interface
- Download of single or multiple files based on a cart system

- Providing provenance information on dataset landing pages and in data files
- Statistics of data usage: number of downloads, of citations, etc.
- Subscription system to the datasets that will keep inform users of events on the data sets (new data, new versions, etc.)

Milestones:

- March 2022: Release of the new IAGOS Data Portal

2.1.6.4. *ICOS Implementation Plan - GUI recommendations*

ICOS considers that its GUI interfaces are already mature and currently in the phase of active maintenance. Continuous improvements based on users experience and requests are implemented.

Milestones:

- none

2.1.6.5. *SIOS Implementation Plan - GUI recommendations*

A major update of the data portal will take place in mid 2021, in line with the GUI recommendations. This will include an upgrade of the CMS (Drupal 8) and support for a new search interface with faceted search filters and support for linked data for specific fields. GDPR consent will be included. The new data portal will include:

- new search interface
- inclusion of dynamically updated results based on filters
- filters: dataset level (parent/child), isotopic categories, project, organization personnel and data centres
- full text search (with auto-populated suggestions), time, location and variables (as recommended)
- metadata information both as landing pages and popups
- metadata information will be provided, when applicable, as a clickable link for license as well as platform and instrument (wmo)
- citation elements will be exposed if provided by the data providers
- location search through openstreetmap widget
- access of single files will depend on the format provided by the data providers in the metadata (support is in place for http(s), OPeNDAP, WMS)
- visualization tools are extended for time series profiles and gridded data

As SIOS is not hosting datasets but only exposing metadata from the participating data centres, the authoritative landing pages will be exposed as URL and are not part of the SIOS data portal. Nevertheless, local landing pages with metadata information will include the metadata identifier.

In 2022 a further step towards linked data will be included by providing links for metadata-controlled vocabulary using the local vocabulary server developed through ENVRI-FAIR (WP4).

In 2022 further development for download and visualization of multiple datasets will be done.

Milestones:

- Release of the sios-svalbard.org (summer 2021)

2.1.7. Documenting provenance

Provenance entails making each execution of an RI data production workflow traceable, i.e. a data point can be traced back to the time of measurement.

As defined in the progress report provided by the WP8 Provenance working group, each RI should follow the following steps for the implementation of provenance metadata management:

1. Describe the data production workflow using graph representation
2. Use PROV-O
3. Optional: implement PROV-Template to describe all the provenance workflows within an RI and be able to control the provenance profiles for each dataset.
4. Recommended: Implement a triple store to store provenance metadata.
5. Provide the provenance information to the users through the landing pages of the data sets and if possible in data files.

It is recommended to provide provenance on the landing page of the data set in human and machine-readable way. The data files should at least include the PID of the data set which is a redirection to the landing page containing the provenance information.

The data files could also contain some provenance information as proposed in the CF and ACCD conventions for the NetCDF format.

Provenance metadata of a dataset should contain:

- PID of the dataset(s) of origin
- Description of the process(es) used for the creation of the dataset:
 - Date time of the process
 - PID of the software used for the processing
 - PID of the person in charge of the process. Additional information should be provided such as: last name, first name, email, institution (if possible PID, address, email, etc.) and the role (the ISO role code could be used:

https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/wiki/index.php/ISO_19115_and_19115-2_CodeList_Dictionaries#CI_RoleCode).

It's up to each RI, according to its capability, to determine the richness and granularity of the metadata. ISO 19115 Lineage schema could be used for the description of the processes.

(see <https://schemas.isotc211.org/19115/-1/mrl/1.3.0/>)

2.1.7.1. ACTRIS Implementation Plan - provenance

Having been an active member of the WP8 provenance working group, ACTRIS will implement provenance documentation as described in the task description above. Even though ACTRIS data production involved the thematic DC units as well as the thematic Topic Centres facilitating instrument and data quality assurance, data production is centralised at the DC units, allowing for an efficient implementation of provenance documentation.

Milestones:

- Implement first test version by autumn 2022.
- Final version by summer 2023.

2.1.7.2. EISCAT_3D Implementation Plan - provenance

The EISCAT data goes through a number of stages of different nature. Some are relatively simple like filtering and some more complicated such as the derivation of physical parameters. Also, the hardware sometimes goes through various levels of development. Most of these are well documented but most of them are not machine ingestible, In recent years, there some effort has been spent on making some of them at least restful linkable in the metadata, like software versioned in GitLab repositories.

Milestones:

- Autumn 2021
 - Complement the hdf5 format of level 3 data, with a more complete set of provenance links
 - Convert the level 1 and 2 data to hdf5 file format, with provenance info
- Spring 2022
 - Create the provenance PIDs following an agreed schema

2.1.7.3. IAGOS Implementation Plan - provenance

Some provenance information is already stored in the IAGOS database but not published in a standard way. The management of IAGOS provenance metadata by a new workflow management system is in progress. A triple store is being implemented to store the metadata following PROV-O standard. In order to enrich the existing metadata, missing information have been identified and will be asked to the data providers. ePIC PIDs will be used for all the entities managed by the workflow (software, data sets, instruments, etc.)

The provenance metadata will be provided as followed:

- A landing page will be available for each entity (containing versioning information)
- On each landing page there will be possibility to browse the whole processing chain between the entities, between the versions
- Some provenance information will be provided in the data files (following CF and ACDD standards). At least the PID of the landing page will be provided.
- A citation system will be implemented for high level products based on DOI fragments: querystore, query landing pages, etc.

Milestones:

- December 2021: management of DOI fragments and implementation of a querystore
- December 2021: consistent use of PIDs and new data production workflow implemented
- March 2022: Release of the new IAGOS Data Portal

2.1.7.4. ICOS Implementation Plan - provenance

ICOS provenance metadata is modelled following a simplified version of PROV-O and implemented using the linked data approach. All data objects are linked to PIDs (Handle and DOI) that reference through our linked data system to the provenance of the data objects concerning data origin (contributor, submitter, station, instrument), spatial and temporal (time coverage, data submission, data processing) information. In the framework of ENVRIFAIR missing elements on provenance will be added to the ontology with regards to instruments and data processing through streamlining of the metadata at the Thematic Centres and exchange with the Carbon Portal, similar to the setup of data exchange for attribution and roles.

Milestones:

- Spring 2022: Implementation of the improved provenance scheme for instruments and data processing linked to the Level 2 data sets

2.1.7.5. SIOS Implementation Plan - provenance

SIOS does not host or manage data directly, but only harvesting discovery metadata from the contributing centres, thus is missing the requirements to fully implement a data provenance workflow. On the other hand SIOS will use a METNO use case to provide minimal provenance information extracted from netCDF files that are hosted in the METNO repository and exposed through the SIOS web portal. Inclusion of provenance will be done through a modification of the internal metadata standard, which is necessary to pick up the relevant elements within the files. The information will be part of the new metadata items that are stored and indexed. These will be then provided on the data portal together with the metadata information for each dataset. A possible mapping between available metadata and PROV-O will be evaluated.

Milestones:

- Expose minimal provenance information on the SIOS web portal for selected datasets that are hosted at METNO (end 2022)

2.2. Essential tasks for immediate implementation planning

For each of the tasks in this section, a working group is set up to specify implementation planning.

2.2.1. Domain vocabulary / ontology for observed parameters, discovery and use metadata

The ontology for the ENVRI atmospheric domain should reflect the time independent inner logic of properties to be organised, rather than referring to other organisational structures which have a tendency to change with time. It should re-use existing vocabularies wherever possible. The first action items will consist of:

- Defining the ontology scope. Which properties should be covered, taking into account size of and resources for the task.
- Mapping of existing vocabularies, assess their suitability for being used in the ontology, identify gaps in vocabularies.

This task will connect to ENVRI-FAIR WP7, which works on common requirements for (meta)data services and cataloguing.

Lead: Markus Fiebig (ACTRIS)

Participants: Lara Ferrighi (SIOS), Barbara Magagna (ENVRI-FAIR WP5), Damien Boulanger (IAGOS), Claudio D'Onofrio (ICOS), Giuseppe d'Amico (ACTRIS), Vincent Douet (ACTRIS), Bénédicte Picquet-Varrault (ACTRIS).

Aim to be ready with implementation plan: 31 April 2020 (MS45, MS8.3)

2.2.1.1. Work Plan

Terminologies follow a hierarchy of terms, starting from controlled lists of vocabulary, via glossaries (lists of terms with definitions), taxonomies (adding the hierarchy of terms), thesaurus (setting the terms in a relation) to an ontology (strict order and relation of terms). In its constituting telecon, the WG concluded that the largest need in the atmospheric subdomain concerns harmonised vocabulary and

glossaries for documenting data with machine-actionable, rich use metadata, documenting provenance, but also for enabling semantic search. Organising terms following higher semantic principles would be beneficial, but controlled lists of vocabulary and glossary should be prioritised. The working group screened existing, domain specific controlled vocabularies for their potential use and extension in the WP8 ontology WG. The vocabulary defined for the WIGOS Metadata Record (WMDR) as part of the WMO Integrated Global Observing System (WIGOS) appeared to be a good starting point. However, further investigation revealed governance issues, with limited options for the ENVRI-FAIR RIs to influence processes at WMO.

The most prominent concepts where a common vocabulary is needed in the ENVRI atmospheric subdomain concern observed variables and instrument types. For vocabulary on observed variables, this includes the use cases of:

- precisely describing observation data when delivering them to the end user.
- searching observation data in a search portal through structured search, which requires a variable level of detail in the terms used.

A further analysis, guided by WP7 experts, of the existing landscape concerning domain vocabulary and related initiatives resulted in the following tasks for the WG:

1. Obtaining a common reference vocabulary for the ENVRI atmospheric subdomain. This task will re-use the Climate Forecast (CF) conventions standard names for atmospheric constituents. CF standard names are maintained by the community, offer precise definitions of in the name and the associated definition text, and offer a machine-actionable repository. The task inspects the list of CF standard names for completeness with respect to RIs needs, proposes new names where missing, and follows them through the approval process.
2. Taking into use the [Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology \(I-ADOPT\)](#) framework defined by the corresponding RDA working group. The I-ADOPT framework assembles variable names from individual concepts, each with their own well-defined vocabulary. This allows for customised variable terms with a level of detail adapted to the use case while maintaining machine-readable relations. The CF standard names will be mapped onto the I-ADOPT framework. This WG will contribute to the mapping.

2.2.1.2. Timeline

1. Finish completing list of CF standard names with terms needed by subdomain RIs, but missing so far (June 2021)
2. Follow process of accepting proposed standard names (December 2021)
3. Contributing to mapping of CF standard names onto I-ADOPT framework (Autumn 2021).

2.2.1.3. Interaction with ENVRI-FAIR WP5 Expert Environment

The WG has constant interaction with WP7 through WG members representing WP7, which actively guide the vocabulary building process. The group collaborates with TF4 of WP5, which work on metadata vocabulary at the cross-domain level.

2.2.2. Consistent documentation of provenance throughout data production workflow

Provenance entails making each execution of an RI data production workflow traceable, i.e. a data point can be traced back to the time of measurement. This task will identify a provenance scheme suitable for atmospheric ENVRI RIs, and will develop a concept for implementing it. The first measure will be one or several training events for RI provenance focal points. These will then work on the provenance implementation in one or several workshops.

This task is to link to the respective efforts in ENVRI-FAIR WP7, which targets implementation support across ENVRI-FAIR.

Lead: Damien Boulanger (IAGOS)

Participants: Barbara Magagna (ENVRI-FAIR WP5), Lara Ferrighi (SIOS), Alex Vermeulen (ICOS), Markus Fiebig (ACTRIS), Ingemar Häggström (EISCAT), Markus Stocker (ENVRI-FAIR WP7), Doron Goldfarb (ENVRI-FAIR WP7).

Aim to be ready with implementation plan: 31 October 2020.

2.2.2.1. Work Plan

The working group had its first meeting in November 2019 when experts from WP7 shared their knowledge about provenance. It allowed all the RIs to understand the requirements for provenance implementation in their data production workflow.

The first action has been to assess the level of implementation in each RI. The group concluded that, with the exception of ICOS, almost all RIs lack provenance implementation so far.

The requirements for provenance implementation are:

- The use of PIDs in each RI data workflow as all entities and agents that are part of the provenance need to be referable. This part is linked to and dependent on the task for immediate implementation “Consolidation of consistent use of PIDs throughout data production workflow”.
- The use of a standard provenance model. All RIs agreed to implement the PROV standard developed by W3C, more precisely the PROV-O implementation (i.e. RDF implementation of the PROV Data Model).
- To have a triple store to manage and query the provenance information.
- The integration of provenance management in each RI data workflow.
- Provide the provenance information to the users. At least two RIs want to provide the information in NetCDF data files. The solution of NetCDF-LD is currently under investigation. The group needs to determine how to provide the information on landing pages. Different user’s profiles have to be considered: data managers will use the complete provenance data for workflow management (machine readable), scientific users will need a filtered subset of this data (human readable).
- Ontologies can be used to name entities, agents and activities that are part of the provenance workflow. It has been decided that for starting, each RI will choose the vocabularies they want. The group will interact later with the Working Group on Ontologies.

In order to gain expertise on provenance, a work plan has then been defined for each RI as follows:

1. Describe its data production workflow using graph representation in order to have a schema for provenance information. Provenance information will be data instantiated from executing the workflow schema.
2. Implement PROV-O on several workflow elements for testing purposes.
3. If necessary, implement PROV-Template to describe all the provenance workflows within an RI and be able to control the provenance profiles for each dataset. The tool developed during ENVRIplus will be used.
4. Implement a triple store. This part isn’t mandatory as some RIs can choose to use tools such as ProvToolbox in Java or Prov Python for PROV-O data generation. Although the use of a triple store is recommended as it will allow for instance to manage provenance data version control and querying.
5. Provide the provenance information to the users through landing pages of data sets and/or in data files.

2.2.2.2. *Timeline*

The working group is having monthly telecons since the November 2019 and will continue until October 2020. More meetings might be scheduled if needed. This task is linked to the immediate implementation of consistent PID use and of the work done in Task Force 4 on Triple Stores. The group will check the existence of training material on provenance. The monthly meetings will allow to check the progress status of each RI.

Demonstration cases will be proposed in order to share expertise. The ENVRI-FAIR Knowledge database UI (<https://envri-fair.github.io/knowledge-base-ui/>) shows the repositories that lack provenance information (R1.2) and links to the corresponding demonstrators. We will use this tool to present our demonstration cases. The demonstrators will be extended, e.g. include also PROVTemplates and SPARQL queries on provenance information.

In October 2020, it is expected that each RI will have enough technical expertise to implement provenance in their data workflow. A short document will be delivered, including all the requirements and recommendations identified by the group. A demonstration on a chosen use case will also be available for the ENVRI community, for training purpose for instance.

2.2.2.3. *Interaction with ENVRI-FAIR WP7 Expert Environment*

WP5 and WP7 experts are active members of the working group and at least one representative always attends the monthly meetings. The lack of knowledge and experience of almost all RIs regarding provenance has been filled by presentations and demonstrations by the experts. This group is also connected to the Task Force 4 of WP5.

2.2.2.4. *Provenance working group, conclusion*

As planned, the working group implemented three demonstrators available in the ENVRI Knowledge Base (<https://envri-fair.github.io/knowledge-base-ui/>):

- ACTRIS provenance demonstrator: <https://hub-binder.mybinder.ovh/user/envri-fair-prov-ce-demonstrator-exlbtwmd/tree>
- IAGOS provenance demonstrator: <https://github.com/envri-fair/iagos-prov>
- SIOS netCDF-LD demonstrator: <https://hub.gke2.mybinder.org/user/ferrighi-netcdf-ld-prototype-hc284r7z/tree>

A progress report summarizes the activities of the working group:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1skTTGP4IdUebV5i3OHZe-KnWrbUas6-SOn5UMiqgVAY/edit?usp=sharing>

It is now considered that all the RIs have the technical expertise to implement provenance and the task has moved to implementation (see section 2.1.7)

2.2.3. Recommendations for licenses on metadata and data

This task comprises work on an overview of licenses and policies currently in use in the atmospheric ENVRI RIs for both data and metadata. In collaboration with WP4, the task is to condense this information into a recommendation for license use. Here, the aspect of licensing metadata, in addition to the data, is to be explored, and the options and implications considered.

This task is to link to the respective efforts in ENVRI-FAIR WP4, which works on common FAIR Policies.

Lead: Leo Rivier (ICOS)

Participants: Cathrine Lund Myhre (ACTRIS), Damien Boulanger (IAGOS), Lara Ferrighi (SIOS), Ingemar Häggström (EISCAT).

Aim to be ready with implementation plan: 31 May 2020.

2.2.3.1. *Work Plan*

ENVRI FAIR Milestone 34 entitled “Existing data policies and licenses in use in the Atmospheric subdomain” was produced. It provides access to reference material for both data policies and licenses used by the 5 Atmosphere RIs ACTRIS, EISCAT, IAGOS, ICOS-Atm, SIOS. It shows that data policies exist for all. However, only ICOS operates with operational license provision for data distribution. Policy harmonization has an imminent political dimension to it. This is to be dealt in ENVRI FAIR WP4. However here we recommend considering the already widely used Creative Commons CC license. In 2017, over 1,4 billion creative commons licenses were at work. This set of licenses is characterised by its ease of use. CC licenses have a three-layer structure: a legal code, a human readable code and a machine readable layer. This last layer is implemented by having all the HTML provided by the CC licenses chooser be automatically annotated with metadata in RDFa format. CC licenses provide a large spectrum from public domain to right reserved licenses. This is implemented by a concise set of icons symbolising different rights, that can be combined. See table below:

Icon	Right	Description
	Attribution (BY)	Licenseses may copy, distribute, display and perform the work and make derivative works and remixes based on it only if they give the author or licensor the credits (attribution) in the manner specified by these. Since version 2.0, all Creative Commons licences require attribution to the creator and include the BY element.
	Share-alike (SA)	Licenseses may distribute derivative works only under a license identical ("not more restrictive") to the license that governs the original work. (See also copyleft .) Without share-alike, derivative works might be sublicensed with compatible but more restrictive license clauses, e.g. CC BY to CC BY-NC.)
	Non-commercial (NC)	Licenseses may copy, distribute, display, and perform the work and make derivative works and remixes based on it only for non-commercial purposes.
	No Derivative Works (ND)	Licenseses may copy, distribute, display and perform only verbatim copies of the work, not derivative works and remixes based on it. Since version 4.0, derivative works are allowed but must not be shared.

A practical and operational implementation of CC4.0 can be seen with the example of ICOS data <https://www.icos-cp.eu/data>.

However, it is recommended against using Creative Commons licenses for software. Instead, we encourage the use of one of the very good software licenses which are already available. Licenses listed as free by the Free Software Foundation and listed as “open source” by the Open Source Initiative could be considered.

2.2.3.2. *Timeline*

Follow progress timeline in WP4 and WP5 for their recommendation on respectively technical and political aspects of licensing and feedback towards the Atmosphere domain.

2.2.3.3. *Interaction with ENVRI-FAIR WP4/5 Expert Environment*

See last paragraph.

2.2.3.4. *Licence working group, conclusion.*

This WG is discontinued since its work is taken care of TF5 in WP5.

2.2.4. Semantic search for atmospheric ENVRI RI user interfaces

This task is on an implementation strategy for semantic search interfaces in data portals operated by the atmospheric ENVRI RIs. This includes:

- Describing and reviewing the state of the art in semantic search interfaces □
Describing typical use case scenarios and their demands
- Reviewing and giving recommendations on implementation technologies.

This task is to link to the respective efforts in ENVRI-FAIR WP7 which supports these implementation efforts.

Lead: Lara Ferrighi (SIOS)

Participants: Paul Eckhardt (ACTRIS), Richard Rud (ACTRIS), Oleg Mirzov (ICOS), Guillaume Brissebrat (IAGOS), Ingemar Häggström (EISCAT), Xiaofeng Liao (WP7) Aim to be ready: 31 May 2020.

2.2.4.1. *Work Plan*

The working group will put effort on gaining knowledge on the topic of semantic search to be able to have some expertise within each RI. More specifically, the focus will be on the different conceptual and technical components that relate to the subject.

A shared Google drive folder has been created and will include several documents, both for internal use and for working on the tasks and deliverable.

The aim is to deliver a document in which we present a short background of the topic and review of existing approaches/efforts in the international community; propose and describe one use case; summarize and suggest a possible implementation to support semantic search within each RI and possibly across RI.

The topic of semantic search is strongly related to other working groups and task forces within the project, thus recommendations and deliverables from other groups should be pointed to in the deliverable. Working group participants will join other relevant working groups and task forces and report back on useful insights during the virtual meetings.

2.2.4.2. *Timeline*

The working group is having telephone conferences approximately every 4/5 weeks. It has been established in November 2019, thus expecting to have a total of 6/7 virtual meetings. More tight meetings might be expected during April and May 2020 to finalize and review the documents to be delivered.

2.2.4.3. *Interaction with ENVRI-FAIR WP7 Expert Environment*

Interaction with experts of WP7 is vital for this working group, both for the lack of previous experience within the participants and for technical guidance and harmonization of approaches with other domains. WP5 and WP7 will shed light upon conceptualization of RDF and linked data, as well as on the implementation of triple stores and SPARQL endpoints.

2.2.4.4. *Semantic search working group, conclusion*

The dedicated group worked on the following tasks:

- Describing and reviewing the state of the art in semantic search interfaces
- Describing typical use case scenarios and their demands
- Reviewing and giving recommendations on implementation technologies.

Knowledge has been built within the RIs on the topic, describing components, approaches and challenges. The outcome of the work is collected in [Redmine](#) including a final report and a prototype:

<https://github.com/xiaofengleo/actris>

In particular, the group has identified challenges for the implementation of such functionality:

- having a robust data model
- giving correct and useful representation of (meta)data
- selecting relevant ontologies/vocabularies
- creating/extending mapping
- use of standards
- efficiency of triple stores/interface additional search engine
- high specialized query languages
- high demand for user-friendly UIs for search

Moreover, as the concept of semantic search is vast and complex, implementations might vary a lot depending on the goals and there is not a simple unique solution. We have concluded that this topic is too demanding to be moved to implementation within the ENVRI-FAIR time frame.

2.2.5. Improve Graphical User Interfaces

A Graphical User Interface (GUI) provides an intuitive way for humans to communicate with a computer system. The same system could be possibly accessed via text-based user interfaces, such as computer terminal, but these kinds of methods typically require deeper knowledge of the underlying system and are generally more suitable for machine-to-machine communication or to serve expert users. A GUI is a better option for users who want to access the offered services without necessarily knowing any details of the back-end API.

The FAIR principles promote data usage by requiring data to be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Having a user-friendly and attractive looking GUI for data portal improves the findable and accessible parts from the human perspective. The interface for humans should not be neglected as it is the key component to engage new users and to serve occasionally visiting ones (see, e.g.,

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/system/files/RDA%20DDP%20IG%20UseCases%20Requirements%20and%20Best%20Practices.pdf>).

This working group aims to analyse and refine the current GUIs of the research infrastructures (RI) in the atmospheric domain. For any RI, a successfully established data portal is one of its most critical components. It is not enough to produce high quality data products; we have to be able to provide first class interfaces for humans to access the data as well. This will make our data more FAIR, and by doing so increases an important key performance indicator: the number of users accessing our services.

Lead: Simo Tukiainen (ACTRIS)

Participants: Simo Tukiainen (ACTRIS), Lauri Kangassalo (ACTRIS), Cathrine Lund Myhre (ACTRIS), Markus Fiebig (ACTRIS), Richard Rud (ACTRIS), Claudio Dema (ACTRIS), Giuseppe d'Amico (ACTRIS), Guillaume Brissebrat (ACTRIS), Jerome Tarniewicz (ICOS), Damien Boulanger (IAGOS), Ingemar Häggström (EISCAT), Lara Ferrighi (SIOS), Markus Stocker (ENVRI-FAIR WP7), Xiaofeng Liao (ENVRI-FAIR WP7) Aim to be ready: 31 May 2020.

2.2.5.1. *Work Plan*

The concrete work plan consists of the following steps:

- Analysis of the existing WP8 RI GUIs. In particular, their technology, design, features, performance, pros / cons and so on.
- The actual GUI revisions. The working group will utilize, for example demonstrations, feedback and peer support.

- Common web-services and modules. Where suitable, develop common web-services and/or modules available for processing, visualizing, searching and/or filtering of data e.g. through Jupyter notebook environments.
- Implementation of identified crucial GUI features using commonly agreed specifications. Each RI will start of by implementing a structured search interface.

This work plan can be just a general framework because, in practice, the different RIs involved have different maturity levels concerning their GUIs. Some have highly advanced GUIs while others have just started to build them. However, because all RIs have fundamentally the same objective, to provide quality controlled atmospheric data products for end users, this working group is a useful forum to exchange information, share best practices and get feedback. The working group is mainly targeted for the developers actually implementing the GUIs.

2.2.5.2. *Timeline*

The GUI working group has arranged a remote meeting every two or three weeks since the end of February 2020. The first few meetings were reserved for overviewing the current status of the different GUIs, as the RIs presented their technology and design choices. In the consequent meetings, the progress of the different RIs were monitored, as they continued to work to improve their existing GUIs.

This work continued until October 2020 when a progress report about GUI WG work was delivered. This report included an analysis of the initial status of the different GUIs, recommendations about the features, options, design etc. for a data portal GUI, and overview of the progress made during the project. In April 2021, requirements for WP8 GUIs were moved into immediate implementation.

The work and meetings continue in 2021, when RIs begin to implement or revise commonly agreed features listed in the GUI recommendations (2.1.6.). The first GUI requirement to be implemented across the RIs is a structured search interface in all relevant GUIs.

2.2.5.3. *Interaction with ENVRI-FAIR WP7 Expert Environment*

WP7 experts are heavily involved in this working group and their expertise is crucial in order to have successful GUI improvements.

2.2.5.4. *GUI working group status update*

The working group has concluded that the WP8 RIs are now mature enough to start implementing the first GUI-related task which is the structured search interface. This task is moved into immediate implementation (see GUI recommendations 2.1.6.).

2.3. Tasks for second half of the project

The following tasks are scheduled for the second half of the project. Tasks that have already been taken up by WGs or implementation tasks are crossed out. This implies that these tasks, despite not having received dedicated implementation tasks, have influenced the work of WP8.

- **Common metadata standards and interfaces for use metadata**
Current metadata M2M interfaces focus on discovery metadata, i.e. metadata elements needed in searches for data. Use metadata comprise items such as uncertainties, data quality and associated measures, operating procedures, etc. This task links to ENVRI-FAIR WP5.
- ~~**Machine readable license and attribution metadata.**~~
~~This task is to specify how license and attribution metadata are to be stored and served in order to make them machine readable. This functionality is a prerequisite for a license broker service, i.e. a service that determines licensing options for a data product based on the licenses of the data serving as input for generating the product. This task links to ENVRI FAIR WPs 4 and 5. Has been taken up by TF5 of WP5.~~
- ~~**Common strategy for structured search interfaces, including common base set of searchable items**~~
~~Structured search interfaces are preferred by expert users with a high knowledge about the data they are searching. This task is to give guidelines for a common architecture of structured search between atmospheric RIs. Has been taken up by WG on Graphical User Interfaces.~~
- **Traceable post-production user feedback services**
Data users routinely find issues with data they are analysing. This task is to work on an interRI service for collecting this feedback. This task links to ENVRI-FAIR WP7.

- **Data indexing in further data portals.**
This addresses data portals considered not mature or relevant enough for the first round of implementation (Google, EOSC, WIGOS). Has been taken up by work around ENVRI-hub and the related implementation task.
- **Standards for RESTful APIs for metadata and data.**
- **Common interfaces for data, facilitating machine readability of data, e.g. in Virtual Research Environment (VRE)s.**
Builds on the previous task for RESTful APIs for metadata and data. This task links to ENVRI FAIR WP5. Has been taken up by WP8 task 8.5 on common demonstrators.
- **PIDs for organisations and instruments to be determined in consultation with experts in ENVRI FAIR WP7.** Has been taken up by implementation task on PIDs

3. Summary

The RIs of the ENVRI atmospheric subdomain have conducted a comprehensive analysis of the FAIRness of their data management. The identified gaps considered most important from a user perspective concern the following FAIRness functions:

- **Findable:** globally unique identifier; indexed in searchable resource.
- **Accessible:** (meta)data retrievable by standardised protocol
- **Interoperable:** common vocabulary
- **Re-usable:** established license, documented provenance, (meta)data meets community standards.

The tasks for implementing these functions were grouped by the following criteria:

1. Importance of the function for the user
2. Maturity of the function in the RI

Accordingly, the tasks were grouped into 3 categories:

1. Immediate implementation: the function implemented is highly important for the user, the implementation plan is consolidated.
2. Immediate implementation planning: the function implemented is highly important for the user, the implementation plan needs to be refined, know-how at the RIs needs to be established.
3. Task for second half of project: the function implemented is considered important, but implementation can be postponed to allow focussed work on the highly important FAIRness functions.

The Gantt-chart below illustrates the timeline of the implementation. Both implementations and task specific, detailed implementation plans will be verified by experts of WPs 5 and 7.

